

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)
Volume I, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication
ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060
Publisher: Binas Publishing
Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

MARL LECHBEN O. GAPUTAN, MPA, LPT
Assistant Professor I
Camiguin Polytechnic State College
nebhcel@gmail.com

“JUST BELIEVE IN YOURSELF”

Problems here and there, it's everywhere
Life is always a struggle, it is not fair
But if you have that inspiration
You're going to get through, no matter the situation

Just believe in yourself
It will only be for a moment my dear
You're going to fly, soar high
Remember the trials you've conquered
You're tough, you deserve to be respected and feared

They say life is a lesson that we all should learn
With all the ups and downs, it's the lessons we yearn
Charge it to our experience
Let us be the wiser one, the good influence

So, believe in yourself
Trust the process and you'll be healed
You're going to be better, better in time
Remember the challenges you went through
Be yourself, to it, always be true

